

STUDIES ON BASIC SULPHATES OF BIVALENT METALS (Cd, Cu, Zn).
PART I. CADMIUM

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The author has studied the basic sulphates of cadmium by thermometric titrations of cadmium sulphate solution with caustic soda solution and *vice versa*. Basic sulphates $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$ and $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \text{CdO}$ have been found to exist.

Literatures on basic sulphates of cadmium show that there are two definite compounds, namely, $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \text{CdO} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Grutzner, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1898, 236, 380) and $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CdO} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Stromeyer, *Schw. J.*, 1818, 22, 367; Kuhn, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1847, 100, 286; Hebermann, *Monatsh.*, 1884, 5, 448). Pickering has reported the existence of another basic salt of the formula $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$ (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1886, 91, 1907). He has observed that on addition of a small quantity of soda to Cd-sulphate solution in presence of phenolphthalein, only the precipitate is coloured pink and the solution shows alkaline reaction only when alkali amounting to 0.731 equivalent has been added. This observation has been explained by him as due to the formation of the basic sulphate $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$, although he has admitted that 0.731 equivalent of alkali does not correspond exactly with the compound $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$. In order to obtain definite indications of the formation of different basic sulphates of cadmium, thermometric titrations of cadmium sulphate with caustic soda solution has been employed here.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The thermometric titration arrangement consists of a Dewar flask placed inside another Dewar flask. The solution to be titrated is taken inside the inner flask. The mouth of the inner vessel is closed by means of a cork provided with three bores. Through one bore passes a Beckmann thermometer reading to the 1/100th of a degree accurately, through the second bore passes a glass stirrer worked mechanically and through the third bore passes the tip of the burette. The burette is jacketed with a glass jacket containing water. The stop-cock of the burette is worked with a rubber-tube. The mouth of the outer Dewar vessel is also closed by means of a three-bored asbestos sheet. The titre is added from the burette to the titrant in the inner flask and changes in the temperature are noted on the Beckmann thermometer after definite intervals of time. The differences in temperature are then plotted against the volume of titre in c.c. added from the burette and the graphs are obtained. The reagents used were of 'Analar' quality. Standard solutions of Cd sulphate were prepared by direct weighing. Caustic soda solutions were prepared by standardising with potassium bi-iodate using Wesslow as an indicator.

TABLE I

CdSO_4 soln. = 0.4954*M*. NaOH soln. = 2.477*M*. CdSO_4 soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 1).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.900°	0.000°	0.000°	11 c.c.	2.600°	0.035°	1.300°
1	3.790	0.110	0.110	12	2.570	0.030	1.330
2	3.640	0.150	0.260	13	2.560	0.010	1.340
3	3.490	0.150	0.410	14	2.560	0.000	1.340
4	3.340	0.150	0.560	16	2.560	0.000	1.340
5	3.190	0.150	0.710	18	2.560	0.000	1.340
6	3.040	0.150	0.860	20	2.560	0.000	1.340
7	2.890	0.150	1.010	22	2.560	0.000	1.340
8	2.780	0.110	1.120	24	2.560	0.000	1.340
9	2.700	0.080	1.200				
10	2.635	0.065	1.265				

TABLE II

CdSO_4 soln. = 0.19992*M*. NaOH soln. = 0.9996*M*. CdSO_4 soln taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 2).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	2.950°	0.000°	0.000°	9.0 c.c.	2.360°	0.020°	0.590°
1	2.910	0.040	0.040	9.5	2.335	0.025	0.615
2	2.835	0.075	0.115	10.0	2.310	0.025	0.640
3	2.760	0.075	0.190	10.5	2.285	0.025	0.665
4	2.685	0.075	0.265	11.0	2.260	0.025	0.690
5	2.610	0.075	0.340	12.0	2.210	0.050	0.740
6	2.540	0.070	0.410	13.0	2.190	0.020	0.760
7	2.470	0.070	0.480	14.0	2.190	0.000	0.760
8	2.405	0.065	0.545	16.0	2.190	0.000	0.760
8.5	2.380	0.025	0.570	18.0	2.190	0.000	0.760
				20.0	2.190	0.000	0.760

TABLE III

CdSO_4 soln.=0.09996*M*. NaOH soln.=0.9996*M*. CdSO_4 soln. taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 3).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	3.570*	0.000*	0.000*	5.5 c.c.	3.220*	0.030*	0.350*
1.0	3.530	0.040	0.040	6.0	3.195	0.025	0.375
2.0	3.460	0.070	0.110	7.0	3.180	0.015	0.390
3.0	3.390	0.070	0.180	8.0	3.165	0.015	0.405
4.0	3.320	0.070	0.250	9.0	3.155	0.010	0.415
4.5	3.285	0.035	0.285				
5.0	3.250	0.035	0.320	10.0	3.145	0.010	0.425

TABLE IV

CdSO_4 soln.=0.05*M*. NaOH soln.=0.4*M*. CdSO_4 soln. taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 4).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0.0 c.c.	4.110*	0.000*	0.000*	6.5 c.c.	3.855*	0.020*	0.255*
1.0	4.060	0.030	0.030	7.0	3.835	0.020	0.275
2.0	4.035	0.045	0.075	7.5	3.820	0.015	0.290
3.0	3.995	0.040	0.115	8.0	3.810	0.010	0.300
4.0	3.965	0.040	0.155	9.0	3.800	0.010	0.310
5.0	3.915	0.040	0.195	10.0	3.790	0.010	0.320
5.5	3.895	0.020	0.215	11.0	3.780	0.010	0.330
6.0	3.875	0.020	0.235	12.0	3.770	0.010	0.340

TABLE V

CdSO_4 soln.=0.025*M*. NaOH soln.=0.39756*M*. CdSO_4 soln. taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 5).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.515*	0.000*	0.000	5.0 c.c.	4.360*	0.010*	0.150*
1.0	4.485	0.030	0.030	6.0	4.350	0.010	0.160
2.0	4.445	0.040	0.070	7.0	4.340	0.010	0.170
2.5	4.425	0.020	0.090	8.0	4.330	0.010	0.180
3.0	4.405	0.020	0.110	9.0	4.320	0.010	0.190
3.5	4.390	0.015	0.125	10.0	4.310	0.010	0.200
4.0	4.375	0.015	0.140				

TABLE VI

CdSO_4 soln.=0.6115*M*. NaOH soln.=0.2959*M*. NaOH soln. taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 6).

CdSO_4 added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	CdSO_4 added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.200*	0.000*	0.000	9 c.c.	3.330*	0.090*	0.880*
1	4.115	0.095	0.095	10	3.280	0.050	0.930
2	4.010	0.105	0.200	11	3.280	0.000	0.930
3	3.910	0.100	0.300	12	3.280	0.000	0.930
4	3.810	0.100	0.400	13	3.270	0.010	0.940
5	3.710	0.100	0.500	14	3.250	0.020	0.960
6	3.610	0.100	0.600	15	3.230	0.020	0.980
7	3.520	0.090	0.690	16	3.210	0.020	1.000
8	3.420	0.100	0.790	17	3.190	0.020	1.020

TABLE VII

CdSO_4 soln. = 0.2959M. NaOH soln. = 0.1598M. NaOH₄ soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 7).

CdSO ₄ added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	CdSO ₄ added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.420°	0.000°	0.000°	12 c.c.	3.040°	0.010°	0.380°
1	3.385	0.035	0.035	13	3.040	0.000	0.380
2	3.345	0.040	0.075	14	3.040	0.000	0.380
3	3.320	0.025	0.100	15	3.030	0.010	0.390
4	3.285	0.035	0.135	16	3.015	0.015	0.405
5	3.250	0.035	0.170	17	3.000	0.015	0.420
6	3.215	0.085	0.205	18	2.990	0.010	0.430
7	3.185	0.030	0.235	19	2.980	0.010	0.440
8	3.150	0.035	0.270	20	2.970	0.010	0.450
9	3.115	0.035	0.305	22	2.930	0.040	0.490
10	3.080	0.035	0.340	24	2.920	0.010	0.500
11	3.050	0.030	0.370	26	2.900	0.020	0.520

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the Figs. 1 to 5 that the basic sulphate $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$ is precipitated by the addition of alkali to cadmium sulphate solutions of strength 0.025M to 0.4954M. But at concentrations 0.1999M and 0.495M of Cd sulphate, the basic sulphate $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \text{CdO}$ is first formed which with excess of caustic soda solution is transformed into $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$. It is peculiar that cadmium hydroxide is not precipitated even when

FIG. 1

NaOH soln. = 2.477M
 CdSO_4 soln. = 0.4954M, taken 40 c.c.

FIG. 2

CdSO_4 soln. = 0.19992M taken 40 c.c.,
 NaOH soln. = 0.9996M.

FIG. 3
NaOH soln. = 0.9996M.
CdSO₄ soln. = 0.09996M, taken 40 c.c.

FIG. 4
NaOH soln. = 0.4M.
CdSO₄ soln. = 0.05M, taken 40 c.c.

FIG 5
NaOH soln. = 0.39756M.
CdSO₄ soln. = 0.025M, taken 40 c.c.

FIG. 6
NaOH soln. = 0.2959M.
CdSO₄ soln. = 0.6115M, taken 40 c.c.

large excess of caustic soda solution has been added to cadmium sulphate solutions. One point, however, is to be noted that although it can be definitely said that the basic sulphate $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \text{CdO}$ exists, no conclusion can be drawn about the number of water molecules attached to it. In spite of the fact that various authors have recorded the existence of the basic sulphate $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CdO} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, no indication of that compound has been observed by this method. The Figs. 6 and 7, i.e., addition of cadmium sulphate solutions to caustic soda solution, show that Cd hydroxide is first precipitated which with more Cd sulphate passes to the basic salt $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CdO}$. Thus it can be concluded that the

FIG. 7
 NaOH soln. = 0.1598M.
 CdSO₄ soln. = 0.2959M, taken 40 c.c.

basic salt CdSO₄.3CdO is very stable and can be obtained either by the addition of alkali to Cd sulphate solution or *vice versa*. Moreover, the common idea which has found place even in certain text-books that when sodium hydroxide solution is added to Cd sulphate solution, Cd hydroxide is precipitated is not correct.

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